

Benzoin Condensation in Dimethylsulfoxide and Dimethyl Formamide

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The cyanide ion catalysed condensation of benzaldehyde in ethanol is a well established reaction¹. The nitrogen analogue of benzaldehyde i.e., benzylideneaniline was also described by Strain to undergo benzoin condensation². However, this condensation of benzylideneaniline has been re-investigated and interesting results have been achieved^{3,4}. Dimethylsulfoxide when used as a solvent in benzylideneaniline, $-\text{CH}_2-$ incorporation between the two mols. of the Schiff's base occurred⁵, giving rise to compound (I) alongwith small amount of benzylaniline (II).

Therefore it was of interest to study the usual benzoin condensation in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) and dimethylformamide (DMF) which is the subject of this communication.

When benzaldehyde in DMSO and catalytic amount of sodium cyanide was allowed to stand at room temperature, overnight, on the addition of ice-cold water gave white crystalline compound m.p. 135° in almost quantitative yield. The same compound was obtained in quantitative yield when DMF was used as the solvent. The mass spectrum of the compound showed M^+ at 214 and other prominent ions at m/e 196, m/e 197, m/e 180 and m/e 107. The ion at m/e 107 was the base peak. The I.R. spectrum indicated the presence of

1. Fuson and Corse, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 975.
2. H. H. Strain, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **50**, 2218.
3. H. D. Becker, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, **29**, 2891.
4. J. S. Sandhu (Unpublished results).
5. H. D. Becker, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1969, **34**, 4163.

OH and C = O groups. The compound was finally confirmed to be benzoin by comparison with an authentic sample. It is quite interesting to note here, DMSO being a powerful oxidant, did not convert the ketol to diketone i.e., benzil. This method seems to be a superior one as it does not need any refluxing and moreover yields are higher. The furfural which gives very low yield in usual benzoin condensation gave 80% yield through this method.

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